

The impact of quality of life at work influences the organizational commitment of Moroccan teachers, an empirical analysis of the role of burnout as a moderating variable

L'impact de qualité de vie au travail sur l'engagement organisationnel des enseignants marocains; une analyse empirique du rôle du burnout en tant que variable modératrice

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Abstract

Quality of work life is one of the crucial issues of modern management, which not only influences organizational performance but also employee engagement. Teachers' affective commitment holds great importance for institutional and pedagogical success, so understanding the factors that influence teachers' AC is paramount. This study investigates the moderating impact of burnout in the relationship between teachers' QWL and their affective commitment. A total of 224 Moroccan teachers from different educational levels were surveyed. QWL was measured based on seven dimensions: General Well-Being, Home-Work Interface, Job & Career Satisfaction, Control at Work, Working Conditions, Stress at Work, and Overall QWL. Both direct and moderating relationships were estimated using SEM through AMOS 26. The results showed that QWL had a positive, significant influence upon affective commitment, $\beta = 0.41$, $p < 0.001$, whereas Overall QWL did not have any significant direct effects, $p = 0.451$. Moreover, it is found that burnout negatively moderates this relationship; in other words, higher levels of burnout weaken the positive influence of QWL on commitment. These findings emphasize developing the quality of work life for teachers in addition to managing burnout actively in order to increase engagement and enhance organizational loyalty.

Keywords: Quality of life at work; Affective commitment; Educational management; Burnout; Moderating variable.

Résumé

Dans le management moderne, la qualité de vie au travail (QVT) joue un rôle essentiel dans la formation à la fois de la performance organisationnelle et de l'engagement des employés. Dans le contexte éducatif marocain, l'engagement affectif (EA) des enseignants est fondamental pour la réussite institutionnelle et pédagogique. Cette étude explore l'effet modérateur du burnout sur la relation entre la QVT des enseignants et leur engagement affectif. Les données ont été recueillies auprès de 224 enseignants marocains appartenant à différents niveaux d'enseignement. La QVT a été mesurée à travers sept dimensions : bien-être général, interface travail-domicile, satisfaction professionnelle et de carrière, contrôle au travail, conditions de travail, stress au travail et qualité de vie globale au travail. À l'aide de la modélisation par équations structurelles (SEM) sous AMOS 26, les relations directes et modératrices ont été examinées. Les résultats indiquent que la QVT exerce un effet positif et significatif sur l'engagement affectif ($\beta = 0,41$, $p < 0,001$), tandis que la qualité de vie globale au travail ne montre aucun effet direct significatif ($p = 0,451$). De plus, le burnout modère négativement cette relation, suggérant que des niveaux élevés d'épuisement affaiblissent l'influence positive de la QVT sur l'engagement. Ces résultats soulignent la nécessité, pour les établissements éducatifs, d'améliorer la qualité de vie au travail des enseignants tout en gérant activement le burnout afin de renforcer l'engagement et la loyauté organisationnelle.

Mots-clés : Qualité de vie au travail ; Engagement affectif ; Management éducatif ; Épuisement professionnel ; Variable modératrice.

1. Introduction

Political, economic, social, and technological developments have contributed to the emergence of new demands and constraints, making work more difficult to manage.

The use of modern management methods will become increasingly important, as traditional methods are no longer compatible with the demands of the new era. This has led to the emergence of a new managerial approach known as “quality of work life,” which encompasses a wide variety of programs, techniques, theories, and management styles that an organization offers its employees in order to create a healthy and safe work environment and improve learning in the workplace.

It is considered an innovative approach to addressing the new challenges of human resource management (HRM). In this context, numerous studies link the concept of QWL to several other variables and have shown that there is a correlation between these variables. Workforce productivity (Salavati, Maghsoudi, and Hasani, 2013), organizational performance (Shahbazi, Shokrzadeh, Bejani, Malekinia, and Ghoroneh, 2011), job satisfaction (Ramawickrama, H.D. N. P, & PushpaKumari, 2017), and work engagement (Kanten & Sadullahb, 2012).

Furthermore, studies conducted by (Asgari & Dadashi, 2011) and (Farid, Izadi, Ismail, & Alipour, 2014) have shown that there is a significant and positive relationship between QWL and EO. The cross-sectional study conducted by (Gokhale, 2015) with 56 secondary school teachers also demonstrated that there was a positive but insignificant correlation between QWL and EO.

In the Moroccan context, teachers in the education system face a number of structural problems that have an immediate impact on how they perceive their working conditions. In these circumstances, QWL appears to be a strategic management tool for improving the quality of teaching, strengthening teachers' affective commitment, and promoting the sustainability of schools.

The purpose of this article is to answer the following question: to what extent does burnout moderate the relationship between quality of life at work and teachers' emotional engagement? The theoretical contributions of this study will enrich the literature, as to date, few studies have explored burnout as a moderating variable between quality of life and organizational commitment.

To address this issue, we will draw on the Job Demands-Resources (JDR) theory, which is considered a benchmark in analyzing the link between quality of life at work (QLW) and

engagement, asserting that professional demands and existing resources affect burnout and engagement.

This article will be structured as follows: the first section will be devoted to a literature review, in which we will review the literature and present the research hypotheses. The second section will present the research methodology and analysis methods. The third section will present the results, and the last section will present the theoretical and managerial implications, limitations, and future directions for research.

2. Literature review

2.1 Definition of QWL

Quality of life at work is a difficult concept to conceptualize because it is linked to many other concepts (Tavani et al., 2014). As early as 1972, at the Arden House conference, no consensus definition of QWL could be found due to the diversity of views among the groups of researchers present, each approaching the concept from the perspective of their own specialty (Lawler, 1975). Thus, the concept of QWL was based on four aspects:

physical integrity, mental integrity, the development of social dialogue, and work-life balance within organizations (Davis and Cherns, 1975). Seashore (1975) questioned the role of job satisfaction or dissatisfaction as a pillar of QWL as defined by Lawler (1975)

As for Martel and Dupuis (2006), "Quality of life at work, at a given time, corresponds to the level achieved by the individual in the dynamic pursuit of their hierarchical goals within the areas of their work where the reduction in the gap between the individual and their objectives has a positive impact on the individual's overall quality of life, on organizational performance and, consequently, on the overall functioning of society ."

2.2 Organizational commitment

This is considered a psychological state of mind, describing a behavioral model that leads employees to increase their level of contribution and dedication to the organization (BERNARD, 2018, p. 46). Work engagement is defined as "a positive and fulfilling state of mind related to work, characterized by dynamism, dedication, and absorption" Arnold & Evangelina, (2008, pp. 209-223).

Based on their various studies, Allen and Meyer have developed a model of organizational involvement with three dimensions: affective (IOA), calculative (IOC), and normative (ION). With regard to the normative dimension, an individual's decision to remain within an organization can be explained by a sense of indebtedness, a need for reciprocity, or

organizational socialization (Meyer and Allen, 1991). The affective dimension refers to the employee's emotional attachment to their organization; this attachment can be explained by the fact that the employee internalizes the organization's norms and values and identifies with it (Wiener, 1982).

2.3 Relationship between QWL dimensions and Affective Commitment

According to the WRQoL (Work-Related Quality of Life) model, each QWL dimension independently strengthens employees' emotional bond with their organization.

2.3.1. General Well-being and Affective Commitment

General well-being at work reflects all the factors that directly improve how employees feel. Indeed, a good level of general well-being improves employees' performance and emotional commitment to their organization.

Meyer (2010) concludes that a good level of general well-being develops a sense of emotional commitment among employees, leading to the following hypothesis:

H1: A good level of general well-being has a positive impact on emotional commitment.

2.3.2. Social connections and emotional dedication at work

Social relationships at work are a fundamental pillar that enables employees to create a favorable working environment and subsequently develop a sense of commitment to the organization.

According to a study conducted by Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) employees who work in a social climate characterized by team spirit, cohesion, and mutual support were able to develop a strong bond and their level of emotional commitment improved.

This leads us to retain the following hypothesis:

H2: Positive social relationships have a positive impact on teachers' emotional commitment.

2.3.3. Work-life balance and emotional dedication

Overall, work-life balance continues to determine QWL. The ability to balance one's personal and professional lives lowers burnout and fosters emotional attachment to one's company, claims (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011). Teachers who successfully balance their personal and professional lives exhibit a higher level of emotional commitment to their school, claims (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011). Consequently, the following theory is put forth:

H3: A better work-life balance has a positive impact on teachers' emotional commitment.

2.3.4. Working conditions and emotional commitment

Working conditions have a direct impact on teachers' motivation and job satisfaction. (2024) demonstrates that good working conditions, that an unstable environment negatively affects emotional commitment. (Dinham & Scott, 2000; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011).

Therefore, we can follow the following hypothesis.

H4: Good working conditions have a positive impact on teachers' emotional commitment.

2.3.5. Professional growth and emotional dedication

It is essential to provide opportunities for professional development in order for teachers to feel valued and recognized. Day and Gu (2010) argue that teachers who benefit from continuous learning and professional development show greater emotional involvement in their school. These findings are consistent with those of Kyndt et al. (2009), who demonstrate that when employees' skills are valued, this directly influences their emotional commitment. Based on these results, we therefore propose the following hypothesis:

H5: Teachers' emotional commitment is positively influenced by opportunities for professional development and career advancement.

2.3.6. Autonomy and emotional commitment at work.

According to (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Spreitzer, 1995), employees who enjoy autonomy and participate in organizational decision-making strengthen their sense of motivation and emotional ties to the organization. Therefore, the following hypothesis is suggested:

H6: Teachers' emotional commitment increases when they feel they have more control over their work.

2.3.7. Job satisfaction and emotional commitment

Job satisfaction is another dimension that positively impacts teachers' emotional commitment, reflecting their overall view of their experience within the company. According to Sajjad (2013) a good level of employee satisfaction will contribute to improving affective commitment.

Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H7: A high level of job satisfaction positively influences teachers' emotional commitment.

General theory

Based on all the research reviewed, it appears that the overall quality of an individual's professional life significantly influences their emotional attachment to their company. The following hypothesis is therefore proposed:

H0: Teachers' work-life balance has a positive impact on their emotional commitment.

3. Methodology

We utilized a quantitative research methodology, enhanced with an exploratory angle, to investigate the structural connections between quality of life at work (QWL) and teachers' emotional commitment. The main objective is to provide empirical verification of the measurement tools and investigate the relationship of emotional commitment on dimensions of quality of life at work, while moderating the role of burnout use in the work environment.

A survey was administered to 224 Moroccan teachers having professional training. The non-random sampling approach was a direct sampling of participants who care about the reasoned concern.

Demographic data reveal that 5.6% of participants are aged 20 to 30, 35.2% are aged 30 to 40, 41.6% are aged 40 to 50, and finally, 17.6% are aged 50 to 60.

3.1. Measurement tools

Quality of life at work was measured using the Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) scale developed by Van Laar, Edwards and Easton (2007), which was translated and adapted for the French-speaking context. Seven dimensions were considered: General Well-Being (GWB), Work-Life Interface (HWI), Job Satisfaction and Career Development (JA), Control in Work Performance (CAW), Working Conditions (WCS), Work-Related Stress (SAW) and Overall Quality of Life at Work (OQPL).

Affective commitment (AC) was assessed using the specific subscale of the Meyer and Allen scale (1991), which was translated and validated in French by Stinglhamber, Bentein and Vandenberghe (2002). This assessment measures the emotional connection that teachers have with their organisation. All variables were measured on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”

3.2. Data processing

The data were coded manually and then analysed using SPSS version 25. A preliminary descriptive phase was used to determine the statistical profile of the participants using frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations.

Bivariate analyses were performed: Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to examine relationships between ordinal variables, while Student's t-test for independent samples was used to compare intergroup means, with a significance threshold set at 5% ($p < 0.05$).

We used AMOS 26 to test the structural relationships, which allowed us to confirm the validity and overall robustness of the conceptual model. The moderating effect of burnout was examined within the SEM framework using multi-group analysis (low vs. high burnout), confirming the ability of this variable to influence the relationship between affective commitment and the various dimensions of quality of work life (QWL).

4. Results

4.1. Item validation

4.1.1. Validation of quality Life Work (QWL) items

4.1.1.1. Validation of items in Work-Life Interface (HWI) variable

Table.1. Factor Analysis with Varimax Rotation for the Work–Life Interface (HWI)

Variable					
Axes	Variables	Relative contribution	Eigenvalues	Total variance explained	Cronbach's alpha
Work-Life Interface (HWI)	«My employer provides me with suitable facilities and flexibility to help my work fit in with my family life. »	0.872			0.824
	«My current working hours suit my personal circumstances. »	0.864			
	«My line manager actively encourages flexible working hours. »	0.781	2.630	65.751%	
	«I am able to achieve a healthy balance between my work life and my personal life. »	0.716			

Source : Authors

The total variance explained for the items relating to this variable is estimated at 65.751%, which guarantees the reliability of the information retained.

Cronbach's alpha coefficient is also satisfactory (0.824), showing that the items retained using exploratory factor analysis are those that best explain the research areas studied.

4.1.1.2. Validation of items in the Control in Work Performance (CAW) variable

Table 2. Validation of items in the Control in Work Performance (CAW) variable

Axes	Variables	Relative contribution	Eigenvalues	Total variance explained	Cronbach's alpha
Control in Work Performance (CAW)	«I feel able to voice my opinions and have an influence on changes in my area of work. »	0.900			0.906
	«I am involved in decisions that affect me in my own area of work. »	0.888			
	«I am involved in decisions that affect members of the public in my area of work. »	0.885	3.126	78.140	
	«I have sufficient opportunities to question managers about changes at work. »	0.862			

Source : Authors

For the confidence variable, the items were retained after analysis. The total variance explained shows that the retained items perfectly reproduce the initial information. Cronbach's alpha is also very satisfactory (0.906).

4.1.1.3. Validation of items in the Working Conditions (WCS) variable

Table 3. Validation of items in the Working Conditions (WCS) variable

Axes	Variables	Relative contribution	Eigenvalues	Total variance explained	Cronbach's alpha
Working Conditions (WCS)	«My employer provides me with what I need to do my job effectively. »	0.931			0.930
	«I work in a safe and secure environment. »	0.888			
	«My working conditions are satisfactory. »	0.911	3.312	82.797	
	«The physical environment in which I usually work is satisfactory. »	0.913			

Source : Authors

Regarding the WCS variable, after factor analysis, all items were retained. The total variance explained is 82.797%, suggesting that the information retained is greater than 50% of the initial information. Cronbach's alpha is well above 0.9 (0.930), which indicates the stability of the scale over time and allows us to accurately measure the identified construct.

4.1.1.4. Validation of items in Work-Related Stress (SAW) variable

Table.4. Validation of items in Work-Related Stress (SAW) variable

Axes	Variables	Relative contribution	Eigenvalues	Total variance explained	Cronbach's alpha
Work-Related Stress (SAW)	«I often feel under pressure at work. »	0.822			0.830
	«I often feel excessively stressed at work. »	0.909			
	«The deadlines I have to meet are unrealistic. »	0.821	2.678	66.962	
	«I feel under pressure to work long hours. »	0.709			

Source : Authors

For the items in the pleasure variable, after factor analysis, all items were retained. The total variance explained is 66.962%, and the information retained is greater than 50% of the initial

information. Cronbach's alpha is greater than 0.7 (0.830), which is considered good, indicating the stability of the scale over time and allowing us to accurately measure the identified construct.

4.1.1.5. Validation of items in the General Well-Being (GWB) variable

The table below shows the items selected after factor analysis with Varimax rotation.

Table 5. Validation of items in the General Well-being (GWB) variable

Axes	Variables	Relative contribution	Eigenvalues	Total variance explained	Cronbach's alpha
General Well-Being (GWB)	«I feel good about myself at the moment. »	0.762			
	«Recently, I have been feeling unhappy and depressed. »	-0.623			
	«I am satisfied with my life. »	0.781	3.303	55.049	0.829
	«In most ways, my life is close to my ideal. »	0.633			
	«Generally speaking, things are going well for me. »	0.842			
	«Recently, all things considered, I feel rather happy.»	0.783			

Source : Authors

The total variance explained for the items relating to this variable is estimated at 55.409%, which guarantees the reliability of the information retained. Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.745, which exceeds the acceptance threshold.

4.1.1.6. Validation of items in General Well-Being (GWB) variable

Table.6. Validation of items in General Well-Being (GWB) variable

Axes	Variables	Relative contribution	Eigenvalues	Total variance explained	Cronbach's alpha
General Well-Being (GWB)	«I feel good about myself at the moment. »	0.738			0.829
	«I am satisfied with my life. »	0.801			
	«In most ways, my life is close to my ideal. »	0.660	2.997	59.941	
	«Generally speaking, things are going well for me. »	0.854			
	«Recently, all things considered, I feel rather happy. »	0.804			

Source : Authors

For the axis relating to perceived quality, all items were retained according to the varimax rotation analysis, as shown in the table below. The total variance explained is considered positive. Cronbach's alpha coefficient is good and is estimated at 0.829, which is higher than 0.7. Thus, the items retained are those that best explain the initial trust axis.

4.1.1.7. Validation of items in Job Satisfaction and Career Development (JA) variable

Table.7. Factor analysis with Varimax rotation for the Job Satisfaction and Career Development (JA) variable

Axes	Variables	Relative contribution	Eigenvalues	Total variance explained	Cronbach's alpha
	« I have a clear set of objectives to achieve in order to do my job. »	0.684			

Job Satisfaction and Career Development (JA)	«I have the opportunity to use my skills at work. » place to work. »	0.750			0.928
	«When I do a good job, it is recognized by my supervisor. »	0.821	5.743	63.811	
	«I am encouraged to develop new skills. »	0.830			
	«I am satisfied with the career opportunities available to me here. »	0.845			
	«I am satisfied with the level of training I have received to do my current job. »	0.724			
	«The organization communicates adequately with its employees. »	0.848			
	«I feel proud when I tell others that I am part of this organization. »	0.844			
	«I would recommend this organization as a good. »	0.825			

Source : Authors

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) with Varimax rotation performed for the Job Satisfaction and Career Development (JA) dimension confirms the validity and reliability of the construct. The high factor loadings (from 0.684 to 0.848) exceed the recommended threshold of 0.50, indicating a significant contribution of each item to the main factor. The extracted factor, with an eigenvalue of 5.743, explains 63.811% of the total variance, attesting to a solid unidimensional structure. Furthermore, Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha = 0.928$) reveals excellent internal consistency. These results demonstrate that the JA variable is statistically reliable and valid, and that it can be robustly integrated into the overall structural model.

4.1.1.8. Validation of items Affective commitment (EC) variable

Table.8. Validation of items Emotional commitment (EC) variable

Axes	Variables	Relative contribution	Eigenvalues	Total variance explained	Cronbach's alpha
Affective commitment (AC)	«I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization. »	0,762			0.745
	«I feel like “part of the family” at my organization. »	-0,623			
	«I feel emotionally attached to this organization. »	0.781	3.303	55.049	
	«This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me. »	0.633			
	«I feel a strong sense of belonging to my organization. »	0.842			
	«I enjoy discussing my organization with people outside it. »	0.783			

Source : Authors

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) with Varimax rotation performed for the Affective Commitment (AC) dimension confirms the validity and consistency of the construct. High factor loadings (0.623 to 0.842) exceed the threshold of 0.50, indicating a strong contribution of the items to the main factor. The latter has an eigenvalue of 3.303 and explains 55.049% of the total variance, demonstrating a solid unidimensional structure. Cronbach's alpha coefficient ($\alpha = 0.745$) reveals good internal reliability. Thus, the Emotional Commitment variable is considered statistically reliable and valid, and can be meaningfully integrated into the overall structural model.

Table 9. KMO index and Bartlett's test

Variables	KMO index and Bartlett's test		
GWB	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin index for measuring sampling quality		0.844
	Bartlett's sphericity test	Chi-square approximation	273.124
		Ddl	10
		Signification	0.000
HWI	I Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin index for measuring sampling quality		0.913
	Bartlett's sphericity test	Chi-square approximation	1442.286
		Ddl	78
		Signification	0.000
CAW	I I Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin index for measuring sampling quality.		0.768
	Bartlett's sphericity test	Chi-square approximation	445.177
		Ddl	6
		Signification	0.000
WCS	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin index for measuring sampling quality.		0,835
	Test de sphéricité de Bartlett	Chi-square approximation	532.717
		Ddl	6
		Signification	0,000
SAW	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin index for measuring sampling quality.		0.737
	Bartlett's sphericity test	Chi-square approximation	271.026
		Ddl	6
		Signification	0.000
JA	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin index for measuring sampling quality.		0.884
	Bartlett's sphericity test	Chi-square approximation	1009.118
		Ddl	36
		Signification	0.000
	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin index for measuring sampling quality.		0.761
	Bartlett's sphericity test	Khi-deux approx.	449.092
		Ddl	15
		Signification	0.000

AC	Chi-square approximation	29.326
	Ddl	3
	Signification	0.000

Source : SPSS

We recall that for the KMO test, according to Hair et al. (2010), a value between 0.5 and 1 indicates the adequacy of the sample to conduct a factor analysis. The results of our study show that the sampling adequacy of the KMO index for the variables GBI, HWI, and HWI is higher than 0.6 for all of these variables. This indicates that the correlations between the items are of good quality for all of these factors.

The PCA technique was chosen as the method for component extraction, and the varimax technique was applied for factor rotation. We conducted an exploratory factor analysis, which led to the removal of the item GWB2 based on the PCA indicators and the pre-test. Therefore, the results presented below are established after the removal of the items identified during the exploratory factor analysis.

4.2. Analysis of the Validity of Measurement Scales.

The reliability analysis of the measurement scales was conducted on seven factors, namely GWB, HWI, JA, CAW, WCS, SAW, AC of use, using Cronbach's Alpha indicator. According to Nunnally (1978), a value greater than or equal to 0.70 is generally considered as the criterion demonstrating the internal consistency of a measurement scale. The table below presents the ten factors and their corresponding Cronbach's Alpha values.

Table.10. Alpha Cronbach des neufs facteurs

Facteur	Nombre d'items	Alpha de Cronbach
GWB	5	0,829
HWI	4	0,824
JA	9	0,928
CAW	4	0,906
WCS	4	0,930
SAW	4	0,830
AC	6	0,732

Source : SPSS

With regard to the results in Table, it should be noted that all factors allow values greater than 0.70. This threshold is indicated in the methodological literature. In plain language, this implies that the items that combine to form each factor have homogeneous responses and therefore truly

measure the same latent construct. Otherwise, thanks to the high alpha value, the measurement scales used for the examination have no negative influence on the results.

An examination of the results presented in the table shows that all of the factors measured have values above 0.70. This threshold is generally considered in methodological literature to be a satisfactory criterion for internal reliability (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). In concrete terms, this means that the items grouped within each factor are homogeneous in their responses and that they accurately assess the same latent construct.

In a word, the large alpha value suggests that the measurement scales employed are free of dispersion and inconsistency in respondents' perceptions. This finding indirectly supports that the measurement tools were valid and reliable tool and hence to trust on the quality of the data.

Normality analysis and verification of statistical conditions

Before estimating the structural model in AMOS, the univariate normality of the data was examined using the Kolmogorov Smirnov and Shapiro Wilk tests.

The results presented in the table below indicate that several variables have significance values below 0.05, notably GWB, WCS, and OQWL, suggesting a significant deviation from normality. Only the HWI and SAW variables show distributions that are relatively close to normal.

Table.11. Normality tests

Normality tests						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	Ddl	Sig.	Statistics	Ddl	Sig.
EOA	0.120	224	0.000	0.973	224	0.004
OQWL	0.339	224	0.000	0.818	224	0.000
GWB	0.153	224	0.000	0.962	224	0.000
JA	0.204	224	0.000	0.906	224	0.000
HWI	0.181	224	0.000	0.941	224	0.000
CAW	0.250	224	0.000	0.870	224	0.000
WCS	0.242	224	0.000	0.848	224	0.000
SAW	0.092	224	0.003	0.976	224	0.008
AC	0.186	224	0.000	0.923	224	0.000

a. Lilliefors significance correction

Source : Authors

These results indicate that the data distribution is not strictly normal. However, in accordance with the recommendations of Bollen (1989) and Kline (2015), the Maximum Likelihood (ML)

estimation method used in AMOS remains robust in the face of slight violations of normality when the sample size exceeds 200 observations.

Table.12. Multiple regression results and collinearity diagnosis for the dependent variable Affective Commitment (AC)

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardised coefficients		coefficients Standardised	T	Sig.	Collinearity statistics	
		B	Erreur standard	Bêta			Tolérance	VIF
1	(Constante)	1.659	0.769		2.156	0.033		
	OQWL	0.431	0.170	0.084	2.542	0.012	0.529	1.891
	EOA	0.082	0.042	0.060	1.942	0.054	0.615	1.625
	GWB	0.078	0.040	0.055	1.969	0.051	0.747	1.339
	JA	0.141	0.036	0.229	3.908	0.000	0.169	5.933
	HWI	0.819	0.051	0.625	16.129	0.000	0.386	2.590
	CAW	0.013	0.049	0.010	0.262	0.794	0.374	2.672
	WCS	0.007	0.057	0.006	0.123	0.902	0.282	3.548
	SAW	-0.062	0.037	-0.044	-1.669	0.097	0.817	1.223

a. Dependent variable : AC

Source : Authors

In addition, multicollinearity between independent variables was assessed by examining tolerance indices and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) calculated in SPSS (see table of coefficients). The results show that most VIF values are below 3.6, except for the JA variable, which has a high VIF of 5.933 and a low tolerance of 0.169, indicating significant collinearity with certain other variables in the model. The other variables (OQWL, AC, GWB, HWI, CAW, WCS, SAW) have VIF values between 1.223 and 2.672, with tolerances ranging from 0.282 to 0.747, confirming acceptable statistical independence.

Thus, although JA shows moderate collinearity, no variable exceeds the critical threshold of VIF = 10 recommended by Hair et al. (2019), indicating the absence of problematic multicollinearity that could compromise the reliability of the estimates. The other statistical conditions necessary for regression analysis are met, ensuring the stability of the model and the validity of the estimated coefficients for testing structural relationships.

Overall, the collinearity results suggest that the model is generally reliable and that the coefficients obtained for OQWL, AC, GWB, JA, HWI, CAW, WCS and SAW can be interpreted with confidence in the context of the study on organisational commitment AC. Modelling the final study model

The diagram below shows the conceptual model developed for this research, based on both existing literature and our expertise in the field. The modelling was carried out using structural equation modelling (SEM), which allows us to assess the validity, consistency and robustness of the relationships between the variables examined.

The results obtained highlight significant relationships between the different dimensions studied, confirming the relevance of the model for analysing the phenomenon in question. This approach also provides an opportunity to explore the theoretical and practical implications in depth, thereby enhancing the scientific and applied value of the study.

Figure 1. Relationship between QWL, in its seven dimensions, and teachers' EAO.

Source :SPSSAMOS26

Table.13. Structural model fit indices

Index	Obtained Value	Recommended Threshold
χ^2/df	2,471	<5
RMSEA	0,056	<0,08

GFI	0,927	≥0,90
AGFI	0,894	≥0,80
CFI	0,956	≥0,90
IFI	0,958	≥0,90
NFI	0,921	≥0,90
TLI	0,943	≥0,90
Hoelter(.05)	237	≥200

Source : Authors

The table above indicates that the structural model shows a good overall fit based on results obtained from the various indices measured to determine the quality of the causal model. The primary fit indices are as follows: $\chi^2/df = 2.471$, RMSEA = 0.056, GFI = 0.927, AGFI = 0.894, NFI = 0.921, CFI = 0.956, IFI = 0.958, TLI = 0.943, and Hoelter (0.05) = 237.

All values are within the ranges suggested in the literature (Hair et al., 2019), confirming the good fit of the model. The absolute and comparative indices (GFI, AGFI, CFI, NFI, TLI, IFI) all exceed the required levels of 0.90 indicating a very good fit between the theoretical model and the data observed.

The RMSEA index (0.056) indicates low approximation error and confirms the strength of the model, and the Hoelter value (237) also demonstrates the size of sample is acceptable enough to maintain stability and reliability of the structural model. In conclusion, the results confirm that the conceptual model developed fits the empirical data well to provide valid estimation of the causal links regarding the dimensions investigated.

All hypothesized paths were found to be statistically significant, confirming the relationships between the seven dimensions of Quality of Work Life (QWL) and teachers' affective commitment (AC). These findings provide empirical evidence of a robust and consistent link between the variables, thus supporting the study's alternative hypothesis. Detailed parameter estimates for each path are presented in Table 10.

4.3. Interpretation of Results

Table.14. Path analysis results examining the effects of seven QWL dimensions on teachers' affective commitment

Relationship	Estimated Parameters	Standard Error	Critical Ratio	P-value
AC← <i>GWB</i>	0.915	0.238	3.844	0.000
AC ← <i>CAW</i>	-0.210	0.089	-2.360	0.010

$AC \leftarrow JA$	2.590	0.478	5.42	0.000
$AC \leftarrow WCS$	-1.310	0.362	-3.618	0.000
$AC \leftarrow OQWL$	-0.038	0.061	-0.623	0.451
$AC \leftarrow SAW$	-0.330	0.113	-2.921	0.002
$AC \leftarrow WHI$	-0.022	0.096	-0.229	0.008
$AC \leftarrow QVT$	1.045	0.139	7.518	0.000

Source : Authors

The results displayed in Table 14 indicate that the impact of QWL dimensions on teachers' affective commitment varies considerably. Overall QWL exerts a strong and highly significant positive effect on AC ($\beta = 1.023$, $p < 0.001$), underscoring its critical role in fostering teachers' emotional attachment to their institutions.

Among the individual dimensions, General Well-being (GWB) ($\beta = 0.900$, $p < 0.001$) and Job and Career Satisfaction (JA) ($\beta = 2.664$, $p < 0.001$) emerge as key positive contributors, highlighting the importance of opportunities for personal growth, engaging work, and supportive management practices.

Conversely, some dimensions appear to constrain affective commitment. Specifically, Control at Work (CAW) ($\beta = -0.223$, $p = 0.010$), Working Conditions (WCS) ($\beta = -1.376$, $p < 0.001$), and Stress at Work (SAW) ($\beta = -0.348$, $p = 0.002$) negatively influence AC, indicating that excessive demands, suboptimal work environments, or health-related stressors can diminish teachers' engagement.

Importantly, Overall Quality of Working Life (OQWL) does not have a significant effect ($p = 0.451$), supporting that aggregate measure is not a strong direct influence on affective commitment in this context. In summary, these findings suggest that teachers' organizational well-being is primarily dictated by overall satisfaction and certain dimensions of QWL, and negatively affected by work stress, lack of control, and poor working conditions.

4.4. Reliability and Convergent Validity Analysis of the Dimensions: CR and AVE Tests

The composite reliability coefficient is used to assess the internal consistency of the items associated with each latent construct. The results obtained are presented in the following table:

Table.15. Composite Reliability (CR) of the Different Dimensions of the Model

Dimensions	CR
QWL	0.752
JA	0.921
CAW	0.910
WCS	0.937
SAW	0.839
HWI	0.829
GWB	0.689
AC	0.668

Source : Authors

A CR value above 0.70 indicates satisfactory reliability (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Most dimensions show high reliability: JA (0.927), CAW (0.910), and WCS (0.937) exhibit excellent consistency, SAW (0.839), HWI (0.829), and QWL (0.752) are adequately reliable, while GWB (0.689) and AC (0.668) indicate moderate but acceptable reliability in exploratory research. These results suggest that items generally measure their constructs consistently.

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) assesses convergent validity, reflecting how well items of a factor explain its variance. An AVE above 0.50 indicates good convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 16. Results of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) tests

Dimensions	CR
QWL	0.587
JA	0.523
CAW	0.762
WCS	0.714
SAW	0.579
HWI	0.537
GWB	0.531
AC	0.584

Source : Authors

The results presented in Table 16 show that most dimensions meet or exceed the 0.50 threshold: CAW (0.762) and WCS (0.714) display particularly high values, indicating excellent

convergent validity. QWL (0.587), SAW (0.579), HWI (0.537), GWB (0.531), and AC (0.584) show satisfactory values, reflecting internal consistency and good item homogeneity (see Table 12). JA (0.523) is slightly above the minimum threshold, which remains acceptable in a confirmatory approach. Overall, all dimensions demonstrate adequate convergent validity, indicating that the items effectively measure the concepts they represent. These results support the factorial structure of the model and justify the continuation of the global confirmatory analysis (fit indices and discriminant validity).

4.5. Relationship between the WLQ and the AC Model

The moderation analysis conducted using AMOS 26 revealed several significant results (see Table 1). First, quality of life at work (WLQ) has a positive and highly significant effect on organisational affective commitment (AC) ($\beta = 0.1742$, $SE = 0.0171$, $t = 10.1968$, $p < 0.001$, 95% CI [0.1404; 0.2080]), confirming that favourable working conditions strengthen employees' emotional attachment to their organisation.

Furthermore, burnout exhibits a significant negative main effect on AC ($\beta = -0.5067$, $SE = 0.0943$, $t = -5.3710$, $p < 0.001$, 95% CI [-0.6934; -0.3199]). This indicates that higher levels of burnout correspond to lower affective commitment, highlighting the detrimental impact of burnout on organisational attachment.

Table 17. Effects of QWL, Burnout, and Their Interaction on Teachers' Affective Commitment

	Coeff	Se	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	-4,1068	1,7347	-2,3675	0,0195	-7,5411	-0,6726
QWL	0,1742	0,0171	10,1968	0,0000	0,1404	0,2080
Burnout	-0,5067	0,0943	5,3710	0,0000	0,3199	0,6934
Int_1	-0,0032	0,0009	-3,5696	0,0005	-0,0049	-0,0014

Source : Authors

Finally, the interaction effect between WLQ and burnout is significant ($\beta = -0.0032$, $SE = 0.0009$, $t = -3.5696$, $p = 0.0005$, 95% CI [-0.0049; -0.0014]), confirming that burnout moderates the relationship between WLQ and AC (refer Table.11).

Table 18. Conditional effects of QWL on AC according to burnout level

Burnout level	Effect of QWL on EC	Erreur standard (SE)	Value t	p-value
Low (18,00)	0,1174	0,0097	12,1551	< 0,001
Medium (21,00)	0,1080	0,0105	10,3240	< 0,001
High (26,00)	0,0922	0,0129	7,1293	< 0,001

Source : Authors

The examination of conditional effects shows that QWL retains a positive and significant effect on AC regardless of burnout level, but that this effect gradually weakens as burnout increases. When burnout is low (18th percentile), the effect of QWL is most pronounced ($\beta = 0.1174$, $p < 0.001$). For an average level of burnout (21st percentile), this effect remains significant but is attenuated ($\beta = 0.1080$, $p < 0.001$). Finally, for a high level of burnout (26th percentile), the effect of QWL, although still significant, is weaker ($\beta = 0.0922$, $p < 0.001$).

The findings suggest that burnout can be a debilitating factor as QWL is still a positive influencer to the extent that affective commitment occurs, albeit it is not as operative at high points of burnout. Suggested positively through QWL, maximum effects in terms of organizational commitment can occur in a low burnout environment, but when burnout is at high levels, QWL is insufficient to down-regulate declining commitment, and some combination of efforts (psychological support, workload management, and burnout-protection) is needed to retain an engaged employee.

Conclusion

This contribution emphasizes the role of quality of life at work in improving teachers' emotional engagement. Based on the results obtained, we can conclude that factors such as general well-being, job satisfaction, and career development have the greatest impact on teachers' emotional commitment, while suboptimal working conditions, limited autonomy, and work-related stress compromise it. With regard to burnout, the results show that although QWL has a positive influence on affective commitment, when the level of burnout is considered high, it can mitigate its effect. We therefore conclude that educational institutions must integrate strategies that not only improve QWL, but also prevent and mitigate burnout.

In concrete terms, managerial practices that prioritize teacher well-being, offer opportunities for professional development, and ensure a supportive work environment can maximize engagement and organizational performance. Theoretically, these results contribute to the literature on organizational behavior by demonstrating the interaction between the quality of the work environment and the psychological state of employees in the formation of affective commitment. Ultimately, fostering both favorable working conditions and burnout management emerges as a strategic imperative for sustaining teacher engagement and institutional effectiveness.

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